

STRENGTH PREDICTION FOR TEXTILE COMPOSITES USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK, PRINCIPLE COMPONENT ANALYSIS AND UNIT CELLS

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Keywords: textile composites, artificial neural network (ANN), principle component analysis (PCA), unit cell (UC)

ABSTRACT

There is no rational failure criterion that can be used for 3D textile composites as they have very complicated mesoscopic architectures and failure mechanisms. An advanced interpolation method called an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) has been employed to solve this problem numerically. However, the ANN based on mesoscale unit cell models requires definition of a large number of input parameters. This substantially increases ANN training time and therefore makes this approach computationally expensive. Therefore principal component analysis (PCA) has been resorted to in order to reduce the number of input parameters of ANN. The ANN has been coded into Abaqus Umat and Vumat user subroutines to describe the progressive failure behaviours of textile composites from virgin state to final failure. This methodology has then been verified by comparing the results from ANN and those from analyses of the unit cell model directly. The application of this methodology has been demonstrated through the simulation of a flat 3D braided textile composite plate impacted by a rigid spherical projectile. Experimental validation of the methodology is under way.

1 INTRODUCTION

Failure of 3D textile composites is an aspect where rational failure criteria have not touched upon yet. To define a failure envelope in a multi-dimensional stress space, conventional strength properties as obtained when the material is subjected to uniaxial stresses would be far from sufficient. Conventional strength criteria aim to construct failure envelopes using a minimum set of strength properties. While there have been huge amount of efforts made in this respect with some achievements published in the literature [1], their applicability has been restricted primarily to UD lamina. There is not yet any phenomenological failure criterion, i.e. having the composites treated as monolithic materials, which is directly applicable to 3D textile composites. While waiting for failure criteria suitable for textile composites to become available, an attempt has been made as a pragmatic approach forward as presented in this paper.

In absence of obvious definition of the minimum set of strength properties for textile composites in general, and simple analytical functions to construct the failure criteria, one would expect that failure under general loading conditions can be reasonably captured only if sufficient, usually very large, number of data points for failure could be collected under all possible loading conditions. Apparently, no one is capable of exhausting all possible combinations of loading conditions. With an appropriate sampling process, however, one might expect that the space can be reasonably covered with a finite set

of data points through a certain interpolation process. The artificial neural network (ANN) systems [2] offer as an ideal methodology for this purpose.

The next question is the generation of sufficient number of data points. For the coverage to be reasonable, a very large number of sampling points will have to be involved, which could easily run into millions, if not more. Experimental means of generating them are simply unthinkable. Numerical testing is the way forward, which needs to be appropriately validated by designated experiments, hopefully consisting of an affordable number of experiments. Mesoscale unit cells (UCs) for 3D textile composites would offer a practical platform for such numerical testing [3].

Textile composites have complex mesoscopic architectures, which make the construction on unit cells complicated and hence the prediction of their effective properties challenging. The approach taken was to parameterize typical textile architectures which results in a sizeable number of parameters [2]. They could be treated as the input to ANN. In general, the more parameters introduced to ANN, the more sampling data points required and the larger the number of neural elements will have to be used, which makes this method more computationally demanding.

An extra complication to the numerical testing is modelling the damage and progressive failure of these composites. If not applied with care, it could invalidate the approach as a whole. It should be reasonable to categorise the damage process into two phases: dispersed and localized. In the present approach, it is assumed that unit cells are applicable to the first phase, and the onset of the second phase is not far from final failure, as is necking to the fracture in the uniaxial tensile tests of mild steel, hence the failure of the material is considered without involving the phase of localization. The effective material properties may vary under applied loads due to the initiation and evolution of damage. Appropriate damage model [5] has been incorporated to predict the degradation of the effective properties in textile composites, increasing the demand on sampling data points and the ANN training time.

The number of input parameters of ANN can be reduced by applying principal component analysis (PCA)[6]. This method defines a set of new variables (principal components) of reduced number, each as a combination of the original set of parameters.

An approach was thus developed using mesoscale UCs to generate sufficient number of data points, PCA to reduce the number of input parameters for ANN to produce a trained ANN system. The outcome is a well-structures data set, an ANN system. It can then be accessed by Abaqus or LS-Dyna through their user material subroutine [7] [8] to define a textile composite as a monolithic material with all its mesoscale features and damage characteristics duly reflected. The approach is applied for predicting the failure of 3D braided composites, which have textile reinforcement architecture as shown in Fig. 1(a). Detailed process is presented in the paper. The application of this methodology is demonstrated through the simulation of a flat 3D braided textile composite plate impacted by a rigid spherical projectile. A more systematic experimental validation programme of the methodology is under way.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Introduction to unit cell theory

Finite element method (FEM) has been widely used for predicting the effective properties of composite materials, especially for modern textile composites [9]. Analyses are often based on micromechanics of composites, where the properties of the constituents and the weave architectures are known. Thus, a representative volume element (RVE)[10][11][12] or unit cell [13][14][15][16]models can be constructed reflecting the weave geometry of the composite and loading conditions under which the material operates. A unit cell model of 3D braided composite is shown in Fig.1 (b).With properties of the constituents (fibre and matrix) appropriately defined, the overall properties of composites can be predicted with a reasonable accuracy by a FEM.

Fig. 1(a) 3D braided composite architecture; (b) unit cell of 3D braided composite

For accurate predictions of equivalent properties of the composite, it is necessary to apply appropriate boundary conditions to a unit cell model. Since most of the textile composites materials have regular periodic microstructures, the stress and strain distributions in the regular microstructure are also periodic. Therefore, the smallest periodic volume of a regular microstructure can be regarded as a unit cell. The unit cell model with periodic boundary condition represents a large regular microstructure. Considering the periodic geometry and continuous displacement field, periodic boundary conditions for cubic unit cells are defined as follows [16]:

$$\begin{cases} (u|_{x=b} - u|_{x=-b})|_{y,z} = 2b\varepsilon_x^0 & (u|_{y=b} - u|_{y=-b})|_{x,z} = 2b\gamma_{xy}^0 & (u|_{z=b} - u|_{z=-b})|_{x,y} = 2b\gamma_{xz}^0 \\ (v|_{x=b} - v|_{x=-b})|_{y,z} = 0 & (v|_{y=b} - v|_{y=-b})|_{x,z} = 2b\varepsilon_y^0 & (v|_{z=b} - v|_{z=-b})|_{x,y} = 2b\gamma_{yz}^0 \\ (w|_{x=b} - w|_{x=-b})|_{y,z} = 0 & (w|_{y=b} - w|_{y=-b})|_{x,z} = 0 & (w|_{z=b} - w|_{z=-b})|_{x,y} = 2b\varepsilon_z^0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where u , v and w are displacements in the unit cell, $2b$ is the dimension of the unit cell, and ε_x^0 , ε_y^0 , ε_z^0 , γ_{xy}^0 , γ_{xz}^0 , γ_{yz}^0 are the average strains in the material represented by the unit cell. Unit cells of hexagonal shape are obtained using different translational symmetries, however, their boundary conditions are derived based on the same principle, namely, the displacements on one part of the boundary of the unit cell are related to those on another part, while involving the macroscopic strains in an appropriate manner [[13][14][15][16]. In present study, hexagonal unit cells are used to represent UD composite during the micro-scale analysis.

With periodic boundary conditions, a model consisting of a number of unit cells should produce identical results as a single unit cell. Schematic drawing of the deformation of periodic unit cells is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.2 Deformation of a periodic unit cell

The periodic boundary conditions for a unit cell require the coordinates of nodes on any pair of opposite faces to be precisely related [14]. For that, the surface mesh of the unit cell has to be created accordingly to satisfy those boundary conditions. Generating a suitable mesh within a single piece of software can be an extremely challenging task for composite models with complex weave architectures, such as 2D and 3D textile composites.

This issue has been successfully resolved by UnitCells©[3][4], which is a fully automated composites characterization tool. It uses Abaqus FEA software [7] as a platform and its Python Script programming facility as a vehicle. UnitCells© draws relevant functions from TexGen[17] to generate the required textile preform configurations, and from Hypermesh[18] to generate appropriate meshes. Appropriate periodic boundary conditions are imposed and precise loads are applied in an automated manner. The effective material properties of the composite are readily obtained from simulation using this tool. The characterisation process is also fully controllable using the visual interfaces to define relevant geometric and material parameters. In this study, UnitCells© was used to generate strain-stress pairs for textile composites material automatically.

2.2 Overview of ANN method

ANN is essentially an advanced interpolation method. It has a complicated structure, which involves numerous neural elements placed in several layers.

Each neural element has several inputs and one output. A schematic drawing of the neural element is shown in Fig. 3 (a).

Fig. 3 (a) A neural element (b) Structure of ANN

In this figure x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n signify the inputs, y is the output, and ω_i are the weight coefficients. The relationship between inputs and output is defined as follows:

$$y = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i x_i - \theta\right) \quad (2)$$

where θ is the threshold and $f(x)$ is the response function, which can be linear or non-linear.

A full ANN has numerous neural elements allocated to several layers. The connection between the neural elements can be varying and therefore there are several types of ANNs[19], which have different architectures and properties. The ANN used here is a feed-forward artificial neural network (FFANN) [20], which has simple architecture and provides an acceptable accuracy of predictions. The neural elements in the same layer are independent, while the neural elements in neighbouring layers are connected interactively. The value of the connected neural elements is transferred through a weight coefficient. The topology of three layers of FFANN is schematically shown in Fig. 3(b).

The parameters of ANN, such as weight coefficients and threshold for every neural element, are determined from a complicated iteration process called training. For that, ANN was integrated in Matlab toolbox, which makes the application of ANN more convenient with less manual intervention.

As a demonstration, consider a unit cell model for unidirectional (UD) composite. The input parameters (fibre volume fraction and material properties of the fibre and matrix) were assigned a range of values to generate the output parameters (effective properties of UD unit cell model). As a result, more than 6000 input and output pairs were generated, half of which was treated as training

cases and another half was treated as testing cases. The training cases were used to determine the ANN parameter values, while the testing cases were used to assess the accuracy of ANN predictions.

Once the ANN parameters are determined through training, the trained ANN can be used to predict the effective properties of material. For verification, the ANN predictions were compared with those of the unit cell model. The normalized effective longitudinal stiffness (E_1) obtained from ANN and unit cell analysis are compared in Table 1. As can be seen, the discrepancies between the ANN and unit cell predictions are lower than 3%, which means the accuracy of ANN is acceptable. If necessary, the accuracy can be further improved by increasing the number of network layers and the number of neural elements in each layer.

Training case			Testing case		
UnitCells@ E_1	ANN E_1	error	UnitCells@ E_1	ANN E_1	error
-0.7328	-0.7313	-0.205%	-0.7328	-0.7313	-0.205%
-0.6154	-0.6183	0.471%	-0.6154	-0.6183	0.471%
-0.4962	-0.4959	-0.060%	-0.4962	-0.4959	-0.060%
-0.3690	-0.3668	-0.596%	-0.3690	-0.3668	-0.596%
-0.0766	-0.0786	2.611%	-0.0766	-0.0786	2.611%
0.0937	0.0923	-1.494%	0.0937	0.0923	-1.494%
0.2826	0.2856	1.062%	0.2826	0.2856	1.062%
0.4948	0.4933	-0.303%	0.4948	0.4933	-0.303%
1.0000	0.9990	-0.100%	1.0000	0.9990	-0.100%

Table 1 Normalized effective longitudinal stiffness from ANN and unit cell

2.3 Basics of principal component analysis

The meso scale unit cell model requires a very large number of input parameters to be defined, which include geometry parameters, material properties of the components and loading stress combinations. If all of these parameters are treated as inputs of ANN, in order to get acceptable results, a large number of neural elements would have to be used. This would result in a very long training time and require a lot of computational resources.

A method called principal component analysis (PCA)[6] has been used to efficiently reduce the number of inputs. The main idea of principal component analysis is that the dimensionality of original data can be reduced by using the statistical methods. This method defines the new variables, called principal components, the combinations of which represent the original variables. Principal components include the sufficient information on the original data sets, which can be potentially correlated, while the principal components themselves are linearly uncorrelated.

The general summary of PCA procedure is as follows:

Step 1: The original data set is normalised.

Step 2: Matrix of correlation coefficients are calculated.

Step 3: Eigenvalues and eigenvectors of correlation coefficient matrix are calculated.

Step 4: Principal components are the eigenvectors associated with first k highest eigenvalues. The number of principal components is defined according to their cumulative contribution rate, which is defined as follows:

$$\text{Cumulative contribution rate} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i}{\sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_i} \quad (3)$$

where λ_i are the eigenvalues of correlation coefficient matrix, p is the total number of eigenvalues and k is the number of principal components. In present study, principal components include sufficient information on the original data set if their cumulative contribution rate is greater than 85%.

Step 5: New data set is derived, where the original data are represented in terms of the principal components. For that, so-called feature vector is formed as a matrix with principal component vectors in columns. The new data set is then calculated by and multiplying the transposed feature vector on the left of the transposed original data set.

Step 6: Once the dimensionality of the original input data is reduced through application of PCA, the new data set can be used to train the ANN instead of using original data.

As a demonstration, the PCA method is applied to UD composite model presented in the previous section. It has eight original input parameters which are fibre volume fraction V_f , Young's modulus of the resin E_m , Poisson's ratio of resin ν_m , longitudinal Young's modulus of fibre E_{f1} , transverse Young's modulus of fibre E_{f2} , longitudinal Poisson's ratio of fibre ν_{f12} , transverse Poisson's ratio of fibre ν_{f23} , longitudinal shear modulus of fibre G_{f12} . The correlation coefficient matrix of normalized input parameters is shown in Table 2.

	V_f	E_m	ν_m	E_{f1}	E_{f2}	ν_{f12}	ν_{f23}	G_{f12}
V_f	0.3331	-0.0080	0.0029	0.0006	0.0031	-0.0034	0.0020	0.0105
E_m	-0.0080	0.3327	0.0066	-0.0020	-0.0020	-0.0002	0.0040	-0.0072
ν_m	0.0029	0.0066	0.3324	0.0011	0.0004	-0.0014	-0.0028	0.0046
E_{f1}	0.0006	-0.0020	0.0011	0.3277	-0.0014	0.0003	0.0027	0.0072
E_{f2}	0.0031	-0.0020	0.0004	-0.0014	0.3281	0.0054	0.0066	0.0056
ν_{f12}	-0.0034	-0.0002	-0.0014	0.0003	0.0054	0.3250	-0.0061	-0.0129
ν_{f23}	0.0020	0.0040	-0.0028	0.0027	0.0066	-0.0061	0.3383	-0.0017
G_{f12}	0.0105	-0.0072	0.0046	0.0072	0.0056	-0.0129	-0.0017	0.3276

Table 2 Correlation coefficient matrix of normalized input parameters.

The eigenvalues and eigenvectors of correlation coefficient matrix have been calculated, and the eigenvalues are as follows:

0.75763, 0.66677, 0.66677, 0.66677, 0.66677, 0.15407, 0.15407, 0.13559

A cumulative contribution rate (equation 3) of first five eigenvalues is greater than 85%, hence the number of principal components is defined as $k=5$. Therefore, five principal components are used to predict the effective properties of UD composite instead of 8 original inputs. Each principal component is a combination of the 8 original inputs.

2.4 Using ANN and PCA for characterization of textile composites

With ANN and PCA, the effective properties of meso scale model can be predicted for any loading case. The road map of the method is schematically presented in Fig. 4, and the procedure is as follows:

1: Large number of inputs and outputs for unit cell model is generated by running a Python script in Abaqus .

2: The PCA procedure programmed into Matlab is used to reduce the dimensionality of input data. The simplified inputs are regarded as training samples of ANN.

3: An ANN is created in Matlab. Its parameters are determined from training and the parameter values are recorded to a results file.

4: The structure of the trained ANN is coded into user-defined material subroutines of Abaqus or LS-Dyna.

Fig. 4 Road map of using ANN and PCA

For predicting the constitutive behaviour of a textile composite, ANN method is applied at two scales. At a micro scale, yarns within the textile composite can be considered as UD composites, hence ANN for UD composite model is applied to represent the constitutive behaviour of a textile composite at a micro scale. An appropriate user-defined subroutine incorporating the micro-scale ANN is written to calculate the effective stiffnesses and update the stresses. It also takes into account the reduction of appropriate stiffnesses due to the progressive damage of the fibre and matrix, which is an important aspect of failure process in UD composites.

Next, the micro-scale ANN subroutine is used to determine the material properties of the yarns in a meso scale model. The ANN for meso-scale model is implemented into another Umat or Vumat subroutine to obtain the effective properties for the type of textile composite material modelled. Finally, based on the meso-scale ANN subroutine, a macro-scale model is developed, where textile composite is treated as a monolithic material.

3 VERIFICATION

To assess the accuracy of ANN predictions, an ANN was generated to define the material response of UD composite, where progressive damage of the material is defined based on the damage representation and evolution model developed by Li et al.[5][21][22]. In order to make the model simple, properties of the undamaged material as given in Table 3 were kept fixed for all the loading cases.

E_1 (MPa)	E_2 (MPa)	G_{12} (MPa)	G_{23} (MPa)	ν_{12}	ω_0	K
237000	23700	15000	8172	0.29	0	0.4
S_{mt} (MPa)	S_{ms} (MPa)	μ_I	μ_{II}	S_{ft} (MPa)	S_{fc} (MPa)	
300	180	0.0496	0.2	4000	2000	

Table 3 Virgin material properties of UD model

The inputs of ANN are defined as a combination of six strain components, $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \epsilon_3, \gamma_{12}, \gamma_{13}$ and γ_{23} . The outputs of ANN are the six stress components, $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}$ and τ_{23} .

The homogenised UD composite model was loaded at various stress combinations, and strain and stress components of every increment were recorded. Since the stress in fibre direction is not associated with progressive damage, the loading cases are defined as a combination of five stress components.

As an illustration, 242 loading cases were used, with 200 increments defined for each loading case, which results in 48400 pairs of strain-stress combination. Half of these strain-stress combination pairs were used to train ANN, and half were used to verify the outcomes of the ANN.

An ANN with two hidden layer was generated in Matlab, and the number of neural elements in two hidden layers were 34 and 26, respectively. After training, values of all ANN parameters were written to a parameter file.

In order to evaluate the accuracy of trained ANN, the testing case was used to verify the ANN. The normalized effective stress components S_{11} and S_{22} from damage model and from ANN are compared in Table 4.

S_{11} (damage model Umat)	S_{11} (ANN)	error	S_{22} (damage model Umat)	S_{22} (ANN)	error
0.0657	0.0662	-0.806%	0.0589	0.0594	-0.906%
0.0509	0.0515	-1.223%	0.0404	0.0407	-0.802%
0.0432	0.0433	-0.349%	0.0308	0.0306	0.444%
-0.0261	-0.0260	0.566%	-0.0558	-0.0563	-0.765%
-0.0359	-0.0358	0.393%	-0.0681	-0.0685	-0.691%
-0.0460	-0.0458	0.365%	-0.0806	-0.0811	-0.571%
-0.0563	-0.0561	0.397%	-0.0936	-0.0940	-0.428%
-0.0670	-0.0667	0.432%	-0.1069	-0.1072	-0.291%
-0.0780	-0.0776	0.432%	-0.1206	-0.1208	-0.188%
-0.0893	-0.0889	0.385%	-0.1348	-0.1350	-0.129%

Table 4 Verification of trained ANN

Trained ANN is coded into Abaqus Umat/Vumat subroutine. The parameters of ANN are automatically transferred to the subroutine through user defined material properties via the Python script.

For Abaqus Vumat subroutine, only the stress components should be updated. Since the input and output of ANN are strain and stress components, the stress can be updated by calling ANN with current strain directly.

As for Abaqus Umat subroutine, both stress and DDSDD matrix should be updated. Central difference method was used to calculate DDSDD matrix from current strain and stress through ANN.

Stress-strain curves calculated with Abaqus Umat and Vumat subroutines which are based on material model defined by ANN, as well as the stress-strain dependency predicted directly by the damage model subroutine are shown in Fig.5. Here the UD composite unit cell was loaded along the transverse direction. As can be seen, prior to damage initiation (at 300 MPa) the stiffness predictions are identical for all three models, while there is a marginal discrepancy in stress prediction past this point. This indicates a high accuracy of prediction of ANN-based material model.

Fig.5 Stress-strain curve of ANN and original damage model

4 APPLICATION OF ANN METHOD TO MACRO-SCALE MODELLING

ANN for 4 axial 3D braided composites with progressive damage process was generated and coded into Abaqus Umat and Vumat subroutine. The unit cell for this model is shown in Fig. 1 (b).

In this example only stress components were treated as inputs, the geometry parameters were fixed as: $V_f=60\%$, braiding angle= 27° . Material properties of fibre and matrix are given in Table 5, and these values were kept fixed.

Matrix (RTM6)[24]		Fiber (IM7)[23]		Yarn (IM7)	
Density	1.14e3 kg/m ³	Density	1.78e3 kg/m ³	Density	1.716e3 kg/m ³
E	2.89 GPa	E1	276 GPa	E1	248.11 GPa
ν	0.3	E2	19 GPa	E2	17.3 GPa
S	75.0 MPa	ν_{12}	0.28	ν_{12}	0.32
		ν_{23}	0.45	ν_{23}	0.43
		G12	9.5 GPa	G12	6.9 GPa
		St	5670 MPa	Xt	4119.2 MPa
				Xc	2555.6 MPa
				Yt	96.8 MPa
				Yc	440 MPa
				Sa	181.5 MPa
				St	207.2 MPa

Table 5 Material properties of yarn and matrix

The yarns within the textile composite was treated as UD composites, and for them the damage initiation was predicted based on UD composite failure criteria proposed by Hashin[25]. The matrix material in textile composite can be considered isotropic, hence its failure can be described using von Mises failure criterion. Once the failure in the yarns is initiated, the material still retains some of its residual stiffness before the ultimate failure occurs. A damage evolution law proposed by Matzenmiller et al [26] has been adopted and updated to account for stiffness degradation.

As mentioned above, the inputs of this ANN are six strain components and, the outputs are the stress combinations corresponding to each of those strain combinations. Therefore, a combination of six strain components was applied to meso-scale unit cell model, and the output stress combinations were recorded at each increment. The direct strains, ϵ_{11} , ϵ_{22} , ϵ_{33} , were assigned values from the set [0.0, 0.3,-0.3], whereas shear strains, γ_{12} , γ_{13} , γ_{23} , were assigned values from the set [0.0, 0.3]. This resulted in total of 215 strain combinations

All of these 215 load cases were calculated using UnitCells© toolbox. 30 increments was defined for each load case, therefore 6450 strain-stress pairs were generated from the unit cell model. Half of them were treated as a training case and the other half were treated as a testing case. An ANN with two hidden layer was generated in Matlab and the number of neural elements in two hidden layers were 46 and 38, respectively. Comparison of the normalized effective stress components S_{22} and S_{23} in Table 6 shows a good agreement between the predictions obtained directly from the unit cell model as well as from trained ANN material model, which means that the accuracy of the latter one is acceptable.

$S_{22}(UC)$	$S_{22}(ANN)$	error	$S_{23}(UC)$	$S_{23}(ANN)$	error
-0.0226	-0.0225	0.084%	0.0043	0.0043	0.496%
-0.0162	-0.0162	0.051%	0.0078	0.0078	0.201%
-0.0099	-0.0099	-0.054%	0.0113	0.0113	0.160%
-0.0035	-0.0035	-0.155%	0.0148	0.0148	0.083%
0.0028	0.0028	0.665%	0.0183	0.0183	0.081%
0.0092	0.0092	0.319%	0.0219	0.0218	0.042%
0.0155	0.0155	0.204%	0.0254	0.0254	0.044%
0.0219	0.0219	0.189%	0.0289	0.0289	0.019%

0.0282	0.0282	0.189%	0.0324	0.0324	0.023%
0.0346	0.0345	0.148%	0.0359	0.0359	0.003%

Table 6 Verification of ANN for 3D braided composite model

Next, the trained ANN was implemented into Abaqus Umat and Vumat subroutines. These subroutines can now be applied to define the constitutive behaviour of the material at a macro scale. As an illustration, 3D braided composite material model was loaded along X direction. The average stress-strain curves calculated with Umat and Vumat subroutine material models are plotted and compared with the stress-strain curve of original unit cell model as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Stress-strain curve of ANN and unit cell model

As can be seen, the predictions obtained with ANN subroutines agreed well with the result from the original unit cell model. This means this strain to stress ANN is capable to reflect damage initiation and evolution of meso scale textile composites model.

Finally, to predict an ultimate failure of the textile composite, an appropriate failure criterion has been developed. The element is considered to have failed and is deleted from the mesh when its DDSDD matrix becomes singular. An indicator was used to define the element status, where value of unity signifies the failed element, while zero value refers to the active element. This criterion was tested within Abaqus Umat and Vumat ANN subroutines. A homogenised model of 3D braided composites where the material constitutive behaviour is described via either of these subroutines was loaded along X direction, the time histories of average stress and element deletion indicator are shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Stress and element deletion indicator of Umat and Vumat

Fig. 8 Stress contour plot in flat plate impact simulation

As can be seen, the DDSDDDE matrix becomes singular and element deletion condition is activated when stress reaches its maximum, as can be expected at unidirectional loading.

To illustrate the applicability of the developed methodology to predicting the material response at a macro scale, a flat plate impact simulation has been carried out (Fig. 8). The flat plate of 3D braided composite was modelled as monolithic material with its material properties being represented by an ANN Vumat subroutine. Within the Vumat subroutine, ANN was used to update the stresses directly according to the current strain state. ADDSDDE matrix based indicator for element deletion was updated as well.

The validation of modelling predictions via the experiments is the subject of future research.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A multiscale modelling methodology has been developed to predict the constitutive behaviour of textile composite material, incorporating elastic behaviour, progressive damage and an ultimate failure. It employs PCA to reduce the number of input parameters, and an ANN method to define the constitutive behavior of the material at meso and macro scales. This ANN system is implemented into Abaqus Umat and Vumat user subroutines to represent the properties of monolithic textile composites material model at meso and macro scales. Sanity checks have been carried out each stage and scale of the analysis to validate the method. The capability of the methodology has been demonstrated through a simulation of rigid impact of 3D braided composite flat panel.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The financial support from AVIC Commercial Aircraft Engine, Co. Ltd. (ACAE), China, through Grant No. RGS106619 is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Hinton, Failure Criteria in Fibre Reinforced polymer composites: Can any of the predictive theories be trusted? NAFEMS World Congress, Boston, 23rd-26th May 2011
- [2] D. Veit, Simulation in Textile Technology, Elsevier Science, Woodhead Publishing, 2012
- [3] S. Li, UnitCells© User Manual, University of Nottingham, 2012
- [4] S. Li, L.F.C. Jeanmeure, Q. Pan, A composite material characterisation tool: UnitCell. Journal of Engineering mathematics, DOI 10.1007/s10665-014-9776-4, 2015
- [5] T. Yu, S. Li, E. Sitnikova, A Continuum Damage Mechanics Model For UD Composites With The Evolution Law Based On The Damage Driving Force Concept, ICCM 20, 2015.
- [6] L. Smith, tutorial on Principal Components Analysis, February 26, 2002
- [7] Abaqus/CAE User's Manual 6.11, USA, Dassault Systèmes Company, 2011
- [8] LS-Dyna® Keyword user's manual, Volume II Material Models, LSTC, 2012
- [9] S. Li, C. Zhou, H. Yu, L. Li, Formulation of a unit cell of a reduced size for plain weave textile composites. Computational materials science. 50: 1770-1780, 2011.
- [10] P. Suquet, Elements of homogenization for inelastic solid mechanics. in: Homogenization Techniques for Composite Media. Sanchez-Palencia, E. and Zaoui, A. (Eds), Lecture Notes in Physics 272, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 194-278, 1987.

- [11] S. Nemat-Nasser and M. Hori, *Micromechanics: Overall Properties of Heterogeneous Materials*. North-Holland, Oxford, 1999.
- [12] A. Wongsto, S. Li, Micromechanical FE analysis of UD fibre-reinforced composites with fibres distributed at random over the transverse cross-section. *Composites: Part A* 36:1246–1266, 2005
- [13] S. Li, On the unit cell for micromechanical analysis of fibre-reinforced composites. *Proc. Roy. Soc. Lond. A*, 455:815-838, 1999.
- [14] S. Li, General unit cells for micromechanical analyses of unidirectional composites, *Composites A*, 32:815-826, 2000.
- [15] S. Li and A. Wongsto, Unit cells for micromechanical analyses of particle reinforced composites. *Mech. Mater.*, 36:543-572, 2004.
- [16] S. Li, Boundary conditions for unit cells from periodic microstructures and their implications. *Composites Sci. Tech.*, 68:1962-1974, 2008.
- [17] http://texgen.sourceforge.net/index.php/Main_Page
- [18] Altair HyperMesh User's Guide 11.0, www.altair.com
- [19] E. Eğrioglu, G. Aladağ, S. Günay, A new model selection strategy in artificial neural networks. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 195: 591-597, 2008.
- [20] M. Ardestani, Z. Chen, L. Wang, Q. Lian, Y. Liu, J. He, D. Li, Z. Jin, Feed forward artificial neural network to predict contact force at medial knee joint: Application to gait modification. *Neurocomputing*, 139: 114-129, 2014.
- [21] S.Li, M.Wang, L.Jeanmeur, F.Yu, Q.Pan, C.Zhou. Characterization of Matrix Cracking Damaged UD Composites in the CDM Framework, to be published
- [22] S. Li, Q. Pan, T. Yu. Damage evolution law in the framework of continuum damage mechanics for UD composites, The 19th international conference of composite material, 2013.
- [23] HexTow® IM7 product data, <http://www.hexcel.com>, 2010.
- [24] HexFlow® RTM6 product data, <http://www.hexcel.com>, 2009.
- [25] Z. Hashin, Failure criteria for unidirectional fibre composites, *J. Appl. Mech.* 47(2): 329-334, 1980.
- [26] A. Matzenmiller, J. Lubliner, R. Taylor, A constitutive Model for Anisotropic Damage in fibre composite. *Mechanics of materials*, 20(2):125-152, 1995.